

THE INFLUENCE OF CARBON FIBER TYPE AND STRESS-RATIO ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY REINFORCED C/Mg-COMPOSITES

Doris Wurm, Oswin Öttinger and Robert F. Singer
Department of Materials Science
University of Erlangen, D-91058 Erlangen, Germany

ABSTRACT

The fatigue properties of two unidirectionally reinforced carbon fiber magnesium alloys (T300J/AM20 and M40J/AM20) which were manufactured by a gas pressure melt infiltration technique are examined in this study. High cycle fatigue experiments are carried out at 110 Hz and room temperature. The representation of stress versus number of cycles at rupture ($S-N_B$) allows a comparison between the different materials and illustrates the behavior under changing stress ratios. The mechanical results clearly show that the best fatigue properties can be achieved by using the high modulus fiber. The fatigue behavior under different stress ratios is influenced by the interface strength.

INTRODUCTION

The application of lightweight magnesium alloys is an attractive method for reducing mass in automotive and aerospace systems. However, the low stiffness, poor high temperature properties, low wear resistance and the high expansion coefficient [1] limit their use. One solution is to reinforce these alloys with continuous fibers to achieve both light weight and superior mechanical properties.

Carbon fiber reinforced magnesium alloys possess many attractive properties: low density, excellent in-axis mechanical properties (e.g. strength and stiffness) even at elevated temperature [2], very low thermal expansion coefficient [3], moisture resistance [4], and recyclability [5]. Therefore, C/Mg-composites are receiving increased attention for structural applications in the automotive industry where the current trend is towards lightweight construction in both the car-body and the engine. Reducing the reciprocating mass in the engine is of particular interest since it improves the efficiency. Fatigue loads are then unavoidable, and fatigue analysis becomes an important design consideration.

Various factors determine the fatigue properties of MMCs [6]. The fatigue limit depends on the components used (fiber/matrix) and interfacial strength. The representation of stress versus number of cycles at rupture ($S-N_B$) will be used in this paper to study the effect of fiber type. The influence of stress-ratio will also be investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

The composites were manufactured by a gas pressure melt infiltration process. The preforms that were infiltrated were manufactured by a winding technique. Infiltration pressures ranged from 10 to 20 MPa. The composite fabrication process has been described in previous publications [7,8]. Fiber of either high tenacity (T300J) or high modulus (M40J), produced by Toray, were chosen. The volume fraction of fiber reinforcement was approximately 63 vol. %. The properties of these fibers are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of T300J and M40J Carbon Fiber [9]

	T300J	M40J
Tensile Strength (MPa)	4210	4410
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	230	377
Density (g/cm ³)	1.79	1.77

The magnesium alloy AM20 (1.7 - 2.2 wt. %-Al, 0.5 wt. %-Mn, 0.1 wt. %-Zn, bal. Mg [10]) was used as the matrix material. This alloy was selected because of the tendency of the alloying element aluminum to precipitate at the fiber/matrix interface, which increases the off-axis properties without reducing the in-axis properties dramatically [8].

MECHANICAL TESTING

Mechanical characterization of the composites included interlaminar shear, tensile, and compression tests at room temperature were performed with a 100 kN Instron machine.

Axial fatigue tests were carried out at room temperature in a resonanced pulsed machine. High cycle fatigue experiments were run at 110 Hz with sinusoidal load control at different stress-ratios of $R = 0.1, -1, \text{ and } 10$ ($R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$, σ_{\min} = minimum and σ_{\max} = maximum stress in each load cycle). Fatigue tests were stopped after ten million cycles, unless fracture occurred.

The as-cast unidirectionally reinforced composites were machined into round fatigue specimens with a gage length of 9 mm and a diameter of 3.5 mm for testing at the stress ratio of $R = -1$ and 0.1. For $R = 10$ hour-glass specimens were used with a diameter of 3.5 mm.

The fracture surfaces from the fatigue test specimens were characterised with a Philips XL 30 scanning electron microscope (SEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

STATIC STRENGTH OF MATERIALS INVESTIGATED

The results of the static testing for the matrix material and the different composites (all with 63 vol. % carbon fibers) are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the AM20 magnesium alloy with and without carbon fiber reinforcement (σ_{tensile} tensile strength, $\sigma_{\text{compr.}}$ compression strength, ILS interlaminar shear strength, E Young's modulus)

	σ_{tensile} (MPa)	$\sigma_{\text{compr.}}$ (MPa)	ILS (MPa)	E (GPa)
AM20 (unreinforced)	132	225	-	45
AM20/T300J	835	992	68	184
AM20/M40J	1049	634	45	249

The composites with the high modulus fiber M40J were much stiffer and stronger in tension than the composites with the high tenacity fiber T300J. The difference in the interlaminar shear strength depends on the reactivity of the fibers, with the T300J-fiber showing a much higher reactivity than the M40J-fibers [11]. This is reflected by the amount of precipitation at the interface between fiber and matrix. At the T300J-interface many precipitations are observed, in contrast to the high modulus fiber where the precipitations are nearly absent.

INFLUENCE OF THE FIBER TYPE ON FATIGUE BEHAVIOR

Figure 1 shows the S-N_B curves for the composite systems T300J/AM20 and M40J/AM20 obtained during fatigue loading at a stress-ratio of R = -1.

Figure 1. Influence of the carbon fiber type on fatigue strength of unidirectionally reinforced AM20 magnesium alloy

A comparison between the $S-N_B$ curves of the unreinforced matrix and the composites illustrates that reinforcement is very effective. The T300J/AM20 composite is over six times more fatigue resistant than the unreinforced alloy. With the high modulus fiber, the fatigue limit increased by over seven times compared to the matrix.

The influence of fiber type is also apparent from Figure 1. The fiber with the higher tensile modulus produces the better fatigue results.

The data can be mathematically described by the linear equation:

$$\frac{\Delta \sigma}{2} = m \cdot \log N_B + t \quad (1)$$

The slope of the system M40J/AM20 is markedly stronger ($m = -0.50$ MPa) than the one of the system with the high tenacity fiber incorporated into the same matrix ($m = -0.40$ MPa).

In addition to mechanical testing, the crack surfaces of the composites were also investigated. Depending on the fiber type, the systems show different failure modes which are caused by the differences in the fiber/matrix interface strength, see Figure 2.

Figure 2. Fatigue crack surface of a) T300J/AM20 and b) M40J/AM20

The appearance of the T300J/AM20 crack surface is typical of a composite with relatively strong interfacial bonding. The surface is planar, with only a few pullouts. In contrast, the surface of M40J/AM20 exhibits many pullouts. Delaminations of the fiber and matrix can also be seen, caused by crack climbing.

The higher fatigue strength of the composite with the high modulus fiber was to be expected because of its higher tensile strength. Furthermore, the better fatigue resistance of M40J/AM20 can be explained by its weak interface strength which results in a different failure mode. If there exists weak interfacial bonding, the crack can climb along the interface without damaging the fiber [12]. Earlier failure can occur when strong bonding exists because the fibers break at the tip of the crack and the crack can propagate planarly throughout the entire composite.

INFLUENCE OF STRESS-RATIO ON FATIGUE BEHAVIOR

The influence of the stress-ratio on the fatigue behavior is shown in Figure 3 for the system T300J/AM20 and in Figure 4 for the composite M40J/AM20.

Figure 3. Influence of the stress-ratio on the fatigue behavior of T300J/AM20

Figure 4. Influence of the stress-ratio on the fatigue behavior of M40J/AM20

Figure 3 and Figure 4 clearly show the superiority of the MMCs subjected to the pulsating stress relative to the alternating stress. The fatigue strength for a stress-ratio of $R = 0.1$ is better than for stress-ratio of $R = -1$.

Under a stress-ratio of $R = 0.1$, the T300J/AM20 and M40J/AM20 systems have a fatigue limit of approximately 350 and 525 MPa, respectively. At a stress-ratio of 0.1 the superiority of the high modulus fiber become even greater than at $R = -1$ ($\sigma_{\max} = 250$ MPa). This behavior can be attributed to the higher strength and lower interfacial shear strength of this combination.

On the other hand a complete reversal of behavior is found when the pulsating compression range ($R = 10$) is investigated. Under these conditions the system with the high modulus fiber is rather weak; σ_{\max} is approximately -550 MPa. However, the fatigue strength of T300J/AM20 is -700 MPa. These results are in accordance with the static testing, where T300J/AM20 also shows better compression strength than M40J/AM20. The reason for this behavior is probably due to the nature of interfacial bonding. If there is weak bonding of the components, buckling of the fiber can occur much more readily. This can cause the earlier failures under static and cycling compression loading of composites with a low interlaminar shear strength.

It is clear in both diagrams that the slopes of the curves under a stress-ratio of $R = 10$ are smaller than under a pulsating tensile regime. One reason may be that under compression loading crack propagation is inhibited. The fatigue strength under pulsating compression regime is reached at 70 % of the compression strength. In the pulsating tensile regime, the fatigue limit is less than 50 % of the tensile strength.

PREDICTION OF THE FATIGUE LIMIT

Dvorak [13] tried to predict the fatigue limit of unidirectionally reinforced fiber composites with a simple two parameter rule of mixtures model. The applied stress is distributed between matrix and fiber due to the stiffness contribution of the composite. The composite itself is resistant to fatigue as long as both components (fiber/matrix) are mainly elastically cycled. During the first few cycles, plastic straining in the composites is allowable. The fatigue limit of the composite can be determined by the following equation:

$$\sigma_{\max}^c = \frac{2}{1-R} \sigma_Y^m E^c / E^m \quad (2)$$

- σ_{\max}^c : Maximum strength in a fatigue test of the composite
- R : Stress-ratio
- σ_Y^m : Yield strength of the matrix
- E^c : Young's modulus of the composite
- E^m : Young's modulus of the matrix

The fatigue limit was calculated by inserting values obtained through tensile tests into equation (2). The values used are summarized in Table 2. The measured yield strength of AM20 is approximately 40 MPa. The results of the calculation are compared with the measured fatigue strength in Figure 5. The agreement between the calculated and measured values is very good, within 20 %. The only exception is T300J/AM20 in the compression regime, with a calculated value that is half of the measured value. The large difference between calculated and measured values can perhaps be explained by the relatively high interlaminar shear strength. The Dvorak model assumes that fatigue cracks are formed when the matrix starts to deform plastically. It might be that crack initiation is retarded when the fiber interface is very strong and loaded under compression.

Figure 5. Comparison of the calculated and measured fatigue limits

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn from the results obtained in the present investigations:

1. The mechanical results clearly show that high modulus fiber reinforced composites (M40J/AM20) have better fatigue resistance than composites reinforced with high tenacity fibers (T300J/AM20).
2. The fatigue behavior under different stress-ratios is determined by the interface strength. A weak interface leads to high alternating and pulsating tensile fatigue strength. Strong fiber-matrix bonding results in high values in the pulsating compression regime.
3. While the Dvorak prediction of fatigue strength works well for alternating and tensile loadings, it seems to fail in the case of compression stresses and strong interfacial bonding.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support for this work by BMW AG, München, Germany. We wish to thank Ms. S.E. Ellsworth for the critical reading of the manuscript.

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